

ANALYSIS FOR EVALUATING DIGITAL MARKETING TRANSFORMATION OF A BUSINESS BASED ON THE ADKAR MODEL

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Abstract. In this article, a marketing study was conducted to assess the transformation potential of the identified factors. Based on the results obtained, the main problems of digital marketing transformation in business practice in Uzbekistan were identified and scientific proposals and practical recommendations for their solution were given.

Keywords: marketing, digital marketing, transformation, ADKAR model, awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, reinforcement.

The theory of new views on marketing is being put forward by the scientist F. Kotler, who has made a worthy contribution to the development of marketing sciences in the world, based on concepts such as Marketing 4.0. and Marketing 5.0. Traditional marketing theories, which are considered as efforts to understand consumer needs, identify them and effectively satisfy them, are being proposed in a modern direction based on Marketing 4.0. It was concluded that marketing should not only identify and satisfy the needs formed by consumers, but also create these needs, and this is associated with digital transformation.[1]

Marketing 5.0. is characterized by the transition to personalized, data-based and technologically activated methods of working with customers, as the latest evolution of its concepts. This is happening within the framework of "Society 5.0.", a term that refers to the integration of advanced technologies into all elements of society, such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things and big data analysis.[2] The introduction of these technologies into marketing is leading to new and more effective ways to engage and engage with customers.[3]

In addition to these technological advances, Marketing 5.0 is characterized by a greater focus on sustainability and data protection.[4] Businesses are increasingly focusing on the environment and are focusing on sustainable practices and products to enhance their customer experience.[5] This includes adopting eco-friendly packaging, sourcing materials from sustainable sources,

and supporting environmentally friendly manufacturing practices. Additionally, as data breaches continue to increase, organizations are prioritizing data privacy and security to maintain customer trust.[6]

The rise of e-commerce is one of the most significant developments in today's retail landscape. With lockdowns and social distancing measures in place, many consumers have turned to online platforms to purchase goods and services. As a result, the number of businesses operating online is increasing significantly.[7]

The impact of digitalization on manufacturing and services is a hot topic today, and new business models are increasingly being focused on. From the perspective of digitalization, the fourth industrial revolution, also known as Industry 4.0, and its impact on all types of processes is a promising topic in academia, and Industry 4.0 has a significant and formative impact on marketing. In particular, Caliskan A. et al. have conducted research aimed at developing the concept of 7P based on the modern perspectives of Industry 4.0.[8]

Marketers need to learn digital marketing tools and technologies as quickly as possible, adapting them for a particular company. And rapid transformation becomes a means of presenting brands to customers exactly when they need them.[9]

Kasimova M. conducted research on the study and further development of innovative modern methods of bank marketing in the context of digital transformation in Uzbekistan, as well as on improving the areas of increasing the popularity of banking services[10].

The ways of using digital marketing strategies in the development of the viticulture sector were reflected in the research of Usmonova D.[11]. Fayzullayev Sh. conducted research on the issues of developing the activities of enterprises in the context of digital marketing and developed methodological recommendations for their application in agro-industrial enterprises[12].

Proposals for the use of digital marketing in tourism and accommodation establishments and acceleration of digital transformation processes were studied by Salimova, S.[13]. Digital marketing services as information products and services, in particular, based on an intellectual data system and "big data", were studied by Bobojonov B.[14]. Research on the ways of using digital marketing strategies and technologies in the automotive industry was carried out by Akramov T.[15]. Methods of using digital marketing in the field of e-commerce were proposed by Mukimova O.[16]. Yahyokhonov N.[17] created the theoretical and fundamental foundations of the essence of marketing in the

service sector in the conditions of digital transformation of the economy and its application in practice, and summarized scientific views on the relevance, principles, capabilities, tools and technologies of digital marketing. The use of social media marketing strategies in the fashion industry and the virtual activity of fashion campaigns on social networks, increasing the effectiveness of communication processes, Makhmudov T.[18] research is noteworthy. One of the most widely recognized models for understanding the transformation process is the "ADKAR" model. Developed by Prosci, a leading change management research and training organization, the ADKAR model is a model that aims to analyze the behavioral characteristics of people when experiencing change, which are: Awareness: This stage involves understanding why change is needed and what the consequences of the change will be. This is the recognition of the need for change and understanding its reasons. Desire: Once the need for change is recognized, it involves actions aimed at developing the desire or motivation to support the change. This stage focuses on building commitment and understanding the benefits of the change. Knowledge: If motivated to change, the knowledge and skills are needed to successfully implement it. This stage involves acquiring education and resources to ensure that they have the tools they need to manage change. Ability: Having knowledge is not enough. Individuals must also develop the ability to effectively implement change. The focus of this stage is on building practical skills to support, coach, and help people learn new ways of doing things. Reinforcement: Finally, long-term reinforcement mechanisms are put in place to ensure change is sustained. This stage involves recognizing and rewarding individuals for their acceptance of change, as well as removing any remaining barriers or resistance. The ADKAR model suggests that successful transformation requires not only changes in processes and systems, but also changes in behaviors and mindsets at the individual level. By focusing on each stage of the ADKAR model, organizations can successfully implement changes and ensure the sustainability of transformation efforts over time[19]. Traditional marketing is also gradually transforming into digital marketing. To track this process, it is necessary to analyze all the stages that fit into the ADKAR model. The factors that fit into the "ADKAR" model to determine the digital marketing transformation in Uzbekistan are systematized in Table 1.

Table 1

Digital marketing transformation factors that fit the "ADKAR" model

ADKAR steps	Factors
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(Awareness)	Understanding the importance of digital marketing
	Understanding the opportunities of digital marketing
	Understanding the challenges of digital marketing
(Desire)	The need to use digital marketing in your business practice
(Knowledge)	The main reasons for adopting digital marketing:
(Ability)	Market penetration;
(Reinforcement)	Customer acquisition

Additional research is needed to determine the extent to which factors consistent with the "ADKAR" model are being formed. It is not possible to assess the transformation capabilities of enterprises to digital marketing based on quantitative methods. Accordingly, a special questionnaire for the top management of enterprises is used to determine the manifestation of each factor.

The results of the questionnaire will help enterprises to know the level of readiness for digital transformation and make appropriate decisions. It will also provide a more accurate understanding of their readiness to change digital marketing.

The sample questionnaire questions for the test were collected from 100 respondents. The results were processed using the SPSS statistical package.

During the study, 100 business owners were interviewed and asked to fill out the sample questionnaire. The following criteria were established as factors to be considered: "not important" (1 point), "important" (2 points), "very important" (3 points). Based on the survey results, a weighted score was calculated for each factor (1.1) and the relative importance of each factor was determined (formula 1.1):

$$D_i = d_1 + 2d_2 + 3d_3$$

D_i – Weighted assessment of the importance of factors that are important for identifying opportunities for transformation into digital marketing;

d_1 — Percentage of respondents for whom digital marketing transformation is "not important";

d_2 — Percentage of respondents who say they are "important" about their readiness for digital marketing transformation;

d_3 — The percentage of respondents who consider the importance of a factor (formula 1.2) to be “very important” in the digital marketing transformation process is determined by the following formula:

1, 2, 3 — assessment of the importance of the factor (formula 1.2)

$$U_{D_i} = \frac{D_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n D} * 100$$

U_{D_i} — Estimate the weighting coefficient of factors by respondents;

$\sum_{i=1}^n D$ - the maximum possible assessment of the importance of factors according to the respondents' choice;

The weight coefficients of the stages of digital marketing transformation of a business based on the ADKAR model are determined in Table 2 based on formulas (1.1) and (1.2).

Table 2

Determining the weight coefficient of the digital marketing transformation stages of a business based on the ADKAR model

Factors	doesn't matter	matter	very matter	Weighted assessment of the importance of the factor, points (D_i)	Weight of the factor's importance, %
Understanding the importance of digital marketing	12	15	73	261	
Understanding the opportunities of digital marketing	26	24	50	224	
Understanding the challenges of digital marketing	15	35	50	235	
(Awareness)				($\sum D_i / 3$)=240	25,85
The desire to use digital marketing in your business practice	10	16	74	264	

The main reasons for using digital marketing:					
Market penetration;	15	35	50	235	
Customer acquisition	25	26	49	224	
Branding	35	26	39	204	
Competitive advantage	11	19	70	259	
Sales and revenue growth	6	17	77	271	
Sustainability and social and environmental responsibility	49	42	9	160	
(Desire)				$(\sum D_i / 7) = 231$	24,88
knowledge of digital marketing strategies and technologies	55	42	3	148	
staff training and development	62	26	12	150	
(Knowledge)				$(\sum D_i / 2) = 149$	16,05
availability of tools to implement digital marketing strategies	46	29	25	179	
availability of technological infrastructure and support for digital marketing initiatives	41	39	20	179	
qobiliyat (Ability)				$(\sum D_i /$	19,28

				2)=179	
the existence of plans	71	22	7	136	
the accumulation of experience	81	15	4	123	
(Reinforcement)				($\sum D_i / 2$)=129	13,94

According to the results of Table 2, the companies selected for testing the stages of digital marketing transformation of a business recorded 25 percent of results in recognizing the need for change and understanding its reasons. About 50 percent of respondents who participated in the survey understand the need to implement the transformation in terms of the capabilities of digital marketing. However, many business owners still do not have sufficient ideas about the importance of digital marketing and its capabilities.

Business owners do not have the tools to implement digital marketing strategies, support their initiatives, and form a technological infrastructure at a high level. Transformation requires the formation of capabilities. This is justified by the need for greater investments in the formation of technological infrastructure.

Most companies do not have plans or strategic goals for adopting digital marketing practices. It also became clear from the survey results that companies have not yet accumulated sufficient experience in digital marketing practices.

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